

A NEW PHILOSOPHY FOR SUSTAINABLE CONSUMERISM

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ABSTRACT: With growing awareness of unsustainable practices, communities are forcing businesses and governments to take serious steps towards sustainability. Microplastics enter the food chain and eventually reach humans. The threat of global warming and recurrent climate disasters necessitate immediate action. However, all governments and corporations rely on an 'increase in demand' as a growth metric, which prevents them from doing anything meaningful to ensure our planet's long-term viability.

Against the above paradox, this article explores a compromise between sustainability, consumption, and economic growth. It is a theoretical framework for proposing a solution in which businesses can expand in tandem with our planet's long-term future or a glance through the areas where the Keynesian economy can coexist with environmentalists' concerns. The proposed framework claims significance in terms of practicality than the perfection of a solution.

KEY WORDS Sustainability, Sustainable-Consumerism, Theoretical research, Conceptual, Weick's Disciplined Imagination, Consumerism, Sustainable consumption, Green Consumption, Green products, Sustainablism

1. INTRODUCTION

Initially, the term 'consumerism' was in use to "protect the rights of customers through an organized movement (Gilbert, 1999; Jones, Hillier, Comfort; Eastwood, 2005) but, later the usage changed into "a society in which many people formulate their goals in life partly through acquiring goods that they clearly do not need for subsistence or traditional display" (Stearns 1997; Jones et al. 2005). Consumerism is defined as "consumption beyond what is reasonable to meet human needs. The act of purchasing or consuming goods and services as an end in itself" (Centre for Alternative Development Initiatives, 2003 in Jones et al. 2005).

Consumerism is considered as a virtue in a world where all major economies adhere to Keynesian economic ideas (Keynes, 1936), which state that demand is one of the most vital factors in economic progress. Insufficient aggregate demand, according to Keynes, might lead to extended periods of high unemployment and, as a result, economic recession. To avert this dilemma, he claims that all governments should focus on increasing aggregate demand, which is supported by economic evidence. But an ever-growing demand leads to the issue of sustainable development.

Elite scholar Erik Olin Wright asserts "The planet is simply incapable of supporting American-style consumption everywhere. Either we need to stop buying too many "toys" or our consumption of non-renewable "natural capital" has to become orders of magnitude more efficient and restorative" (Wright and Rogers, 2009). It is true that "every product purchased necessitates the extraction, refining, and transportation of raw materials, as well as the use of energy for manufacturing and sometimes use. Finally, at the end of the product's service life (or before), it is disposed either to decompose in landfills or to be recycled, requiring even more energy. Each of these stages impacts negatively on ecological systems and climate change in terms of land use, materials (biological and mineral), water, and climate" (Friends of the Earth, 2010 in Armstrong, 2012).

The United Nations has identified the earth's sustainable future as one of its top priorities. In 1987, they defined sustainable development as 'development, which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs' (Brundtland Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development, United Nations General Assembly, 1987, p-43). However, after more than three decades, the world seems moving away from the aim rather than towards it. The 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Growth in Rio de Janeiro acknowledged the ongoing conflicts between development and the environment and come down with a global plan of action for sustainable development in the twenty-first century, focused on economic, social, and environmental goals. When it comes to consumption and production trends, the United Nations Division for Sustainable Development (2003) reports that the unsustainable pattern of consumption and production, particularly in developed countries, is a key contributor to the continuous destruction of the global environment. Although the cause has been diagnosed, the solution to the problem is significantly more difficult, and the concept of 'sustainable-consumerism' is one idea suggested to help find a solution.

The concept of 'Sustainable-Consumerism' mentioned in this article is a theoretical proposal that is conceptual in nature. The style is more traditional and reverberates the literal meaning of 'Philosophy'. The steps involved in this study are- the development of a concept, scrutiny of the concept through dialectical or rational arguments and accordingly making necessary changes to the concept. Mortimer Adler (2000) in his book, 'How to Think About the Great Ideas: From the Great Books of Western Civilization' argued "In philosophy, the first and basic point of progress comes about through dialectical clarification which gives us an improved understanding of old issues". The procedure is modified adopting a contemporary theoretical research method that is derived from "Theory Building in Applied Disciplines" by Richard A. Swanson and Thomas J. Chermack (2013). In this book, they explain four methods for conceptualization and theory building. Out of the four methods, Weick's method is chosen for this study.

Weick's (1989) theory building as disciplined imagination is the conceptualization process, which he suggests, theorizing as a process involving imagination, representation, and choice. The concern is with how to get the theory-building effort started (Storberg-Walker & Chermack, 2007) and allowing theorists to use their imaginations while developing theories. Therefore, he proposes a non-linear approach and gave theorists three methods to use in developing theories: (1) problem statements, (2) thought trials, and (3) selection criteria (Weick, 1989).

According to Weick, the problem statement should be detailed, clear, and precise. The nature of the problem can be highly practical or theoretical- both are valuable, though the climate of applied disciplines favours application and utility. He further explains that 'thought trials' are different ways to address problem statements. "The key point for theory builders following Weick's approach is to stretch their thinking as widely as possible and entertain a diverse set of assumptions and viable solutions. The selection criteria can be explained as finding a solution that is not distracted by theorist bias and considering an answer fit for different conjectures of a problem" (Swanson and Chermack, 2013).

This study is an effort to bring a model which can accommodate sustainability aspects along with economic growth. This is an attempt to balance between economic development, consumerism, and sustainability. The solution outlined here may allow for corporate growth to coincide with the long-term sustainability of our planet. In other words, it looks at how the Keynesian economy may live with ecological concerns.

The suggested framework favors practicality than finding a flawless answer. The concept discussed here belongs to macroeconomics, with policy changes from governing as well as industry bodies. Testing to validate this idea in its true sense would therefore be challenging. But I suggest this concept as a starting point for further discussion.

2. SUSTAINABLE-CONSUMERISM

Although the term 'sustainable-consumerism' is an oxymoron, it is a coherent method to communicate the goal of achieving sustainability while preserving economic growth. As mentioned, it is an effort to create a model that allows us to envision a scenario where businesses, economic progress, and sustainability can coexist. The "imagination" used to construct this model will be explained in the congruent chronology for clarity of understanding.

2.1. Primary Argument

Based on the logic behind consumerism and sustainability explained in the introduction, it can be considered that these two terms are two opposing notions that are inversely proportionate, with the gap widening through time which is represented in Figure 1.

2.2. Definition of Sustainable consumerism

Based on the above assumption, 'sustainable-consumerism' can be expressed as the bridge between these two curves. It can be translated as 'an area where the act of consumerism will have limited adverse effects on a sustainable future' (Represented in Figure 2).

2.3. The concept

The graphical depiction of Figure 1 may be transformed into a linear framework, as illustrated in Figure 3, to make the subject easier to explain. In this illustration, Sustainable development

and consumerism are represented as the two endpoints of a straight horizontal line that are growing towards opposite sides.

Figure 1. Sustainability and Consumerism on the scale of time

Figure 2. Sustainability and Consumerism with Sustainable-Consumerism on the scale of time

Figure 3. Sustainable development and Consumerism

In this perspective of two extremes, one needs to look for a middle ground between sustainable development and consumerism. This mid-point assumably can describe as the point at which consumption becomes a threat to the planet's long-term existence as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Sustainable development and Consumerism showing the mid-point

This question can be answered by looking at the origins of consumerism, which would lead to the 4Ps of marketing. Consumerism can be traced back to the mid-1950s. As a result of post-World War II overproduction, customers became 'the market'. They were the focus of new product advertisement and marketing. The consumer's appetite does not affect the product's producer, but manufacturers generate artificial demand and preferences for their goods (Dzurová and Pahlková, 2016). In other words, during industrialization, when production exceeded demand, the industry came up with marketing methods to create demand which resulted in consumerism.

4P's that consists of product, price, place, and promotion are the holy grail of marketing as every product must travel through the 4Ps to reach a consumer, or the 4Ps operate as a bridge between buyers and manufacturers. When the 4Ps are passed through a sustainability filter, the variable "product" shines out because if one alters other factors without altering the product, the efforts to achieve sustainability would be in vain.

Therefore, it can be accepted that to achieve sustainability a product must be sustainable.

When we look at 'sustainability' from a consumer point, it can be represented in 3R's- Reduce, reuse and recycle. There may be a lot more elements associated with the sustainability of a product like source of raw material, the energy source used for production, fair wages to labour and so on but for a post-consumer stage, only these three attributes will matter.

Therefore, we will be thinking about the options to combine the 3Rs into a product to make it sustainable.

Reduce and consumerism are contradictory terms. On one side we need to reduce but on the other side need an increase in consumption to keep it going. One of the ways out of this paradox is to increase artisanship in the production stage. Another way to say it is bringing back 'art' in products. There was a time craftsmen use to make custom-made or unique products with high artistic values. Mass production took out the art and uniqueness from those products. If we can bring back the craftsmanship with the help of modern technology, it will help to create a lot more jobs and gives ingenuity to the products.

'Sustain' has been a part of the English language for thousands of years, which comes from the Latin 'sustenare', meaning 'to hold up'. Sustain and its derivatives like sustain, sustainable, and sustaining were first used in a micro or personal context. However, hundreds of years ago, the Swiss and Germans created a method of forestry that sought to keep forests running as productive structures for the long-term, a method known as sustainable forestry in the English-speaking world (Sutton, 2004). According to the Oxford Learners Dictionary, the definition of the word 'sustainability' is used for natural resources and energy in a way that does not affect the environment (www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com, nd). In practice, this concept can be applied by developing products and energy from renewable sources. This original term's meaning can assist in conceiving a way for generating sustainable items, that is, manufacturing them solely from renewable resources.

Back in the 1960s and 1970s, the concept of sustainability grew as there was a need to sustain the entire ecosystem and human society. By the time of the Stockholm UN Conference on the Human Environment in 1972, this usage had become widespread. (Sutton, 2004). Hence, the modern concept of sustainable development has three aspects - economic development, social development, and environmental protection (United Nations' Resolution adopted by the General Assembly, 2005). In that case, the mid-point can redefine with an additional element of fair trade. Trade becomes a 'fair trade' when both sides have taken care of socioeconomic factors, rather than 'profit maximization. Thus, the mid-point can establish as a point where products are made only with renewable resources and procured through fair trade.

While this may address the issue of sustainability, what about consumerism? Anything that is not sustainable may or may not be associated with consumerism. Returning to the concept of consumerism, it states: 'consumption beyond what is reasonable to meet human needs which means anything which is within

reasonable needs to be excused irrespective of being sustainable or not.

Many scholars have worked on the characteristics of a sustainable product, a consolidated list can be found in the article by Dangelico and Pontrandolfo (2010) listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Review of the characteristics of green products (Dangelico and Pontrandolfo, 2010).

Authors	Characteristics associated with the 'green' nature of a product
Elkington and Hailes (1988)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not endangering the health of the consumer or of others Causing no significant damage to the environment during manufacture use or disposal Not consuming a disproportionate amount of energy during manufacture, use and disposal Not causing unnecessary waste, either because of overpackaging or because of an unduly short useful life No use of materials derived from threatened species or threatened environments Not involving unnecessary use or cruelty to animals Not adversely affecting other countries, particularly the third world
Simon (1992)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced raw material, high recycled content Non-polluting manufacture/non-toxic materials No unnecessary animal testing No impact on protected species Low energy consumption during production/use/disposal Minimal or no packaging Reuse/ refillability where possible Long useful life, updating capacity Post-consumer collection/disassembly system Remanufacturing capability
Schmidheiny (1992)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Eliminate or replace product Eliminate or reduce harmful ingredients Substitute environmentally preferred materials or processes Decrease weight or reduce volume Produce concentrated product Produce in bulk Combine the functions of more than one product Produce fewer models or styles Redesign for more efficient use Increase product life span Reduce wasteful packaging Improve reparability Redesign for consumer reuse Remanufacture the product
Peattie (1995)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recyclability Resource efficiency Emissions Impact on ecosystems Social impact Sustainability of resource use Waste and disposal

	Eco-efficiency of production and organization
Robert (1995)	Minimize the use of non-renewable materials Avoid the use of toxic materials Use renewable resources in accordance with their rate of replenishment
Shrivastava and Hart (1995)	Low environmental impact during usage Easily composted, reused, or recycled at the end of their useful life
Roy et al. (1996)	Capable of lessening global environmental problems Energy efficient Easily repairable Designed to last, or to be reused, reconditioned or recycled Generates minimum pollution and waste Can be disposed of safely Minimal use of materials, including packaging Manufactured from renewable or abundant resources, or recycled materials Manufactured, if possible, locally and from locally obtainable materials to reduce transport requirements Environmental information on product available to purchaser Not harmful to human health Satisfies a genuine human need
Luttrupp and Lagerstedt (2006)	Do not use toxic substances and utilize closed loops for necessary but toxic ones Minimize energy and resource consumption in the production phase and transport Use structural features and high-quality materials to minimize weight Minimize energy and resource consumption in the usage phase Promote repair and upgrading Promote long life Invest in better materials, surface treatments or structural arrangements Prearrange upgrading, repair and recycling Promote upgrading, repair and recycling Use as few joining elements as possible
Ljungberg (2007)	Reduce the materials and the use of energy for a product Reduce emissions, dispersion and creation of toxics Increase the amount of recyclable materials Maximize the sustainable use of renewable resources Minimize the service intensity for products and services Extend the useful life for a product Assess and minimize the environmental impact Having a “functional economy” Use “reverse logistics” Increase the efficiency in the usage phase

- Raw materials are sourced from renewable sources;
- Optimum use of chemicals during production of raw materials; avoid wherever possible;
- No harm to endangered species;
- Fair prices are paid during the procurement of raw materials for finished goods;
- Health, safety and socioeconomic factors are taken care of throughout the supply chain;
- Optimum use of raw materials or reduced wastage; zero wastage wherever possible;
- Manufactured without pollution;
- Renewable energy sources during manufacturing, use and disposal;
- Best possible use of human capital to create maximum employment;
- No unnecessary packing;
- Reusable or recycled packing materials;
- Energy-efficient transports are used for logistics needs;
- Durable product;
- Repairable product;
- System for post-consumer product removal and replacement;
- Easy to recycle or painless landfill; Value-added recycling;
- Customers should be aware of the environmental consequence.

A few considerations may help to explain; mass manufacturing with little labour participation may not be the best method to attain sustainability from a social perspective. Handloom fabric production has a lower environmental effect and employs many more people than mass manufacturing (Balaji and Mani 2012; Dissanayake, Perera; Wanniarachchi, 2017). It is reasonable to argue that creating jobs should be considered as a significant positive factor for sustainability, even though output is less productive. Similarly, for value-added recycling, the product's scrap value should be reasonably good. A plastic bottle, for example, produces low-value scrap while aluminium cans provide high-value scrap when recycled (www.sciencing.com).

Thus, the mid-point can be further recapitulated as a point where the end products are made only with renewable resources, manufactured, and transported through energy and pollution-efficient operations, procured through fair-trade, and not consumed beyond basic human needs.

Figure 5. Sustainable development and Consumerism with mid-point with the products are developed only from renewable resources, manufactured and transported through energy and pollution efficient operations, procured through fair-trade, and not consumed beyond basic human needs

The above said is an ‘ideal scenario’, but unfortunately, the world is not a perfect place, and it can only strive to be perfect. The denotation of 'sustainable consumerism' can articulate by merging the mid-point concept with the definition as depicted as a bridge in Figure 2. It is a piece of land in the middle that needs to be decided based on feasibility. Figure 6 depicts a visual representation of the concept of 'sustainable consumerism'.

Because the definitions and scope of the issue change between research, a general notion in an ‘ideal circumstance’ may be reasoned as a sustainable product is created by:

Figure 6. Visual representation of Sustainable development and Consumerism with fixed boundary from the mid-point

This boundary is the representation of relaxation allowed within the sustainable framework, to avoid immediate confrontation while working towards an ideal situation. Again, the limits should decide based on parameters for the short as well as long-term. Goals will be more liberal in the short-term, but rigid guidelines should be institutionalised in the future. Creating short-term and long-term limits are represented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. A visual representation of Sustainable development and Consumerism boundaries for the short-term and long-term

The biggest challenge while deciding the boundaries is a universally acceptable definition for sustainable progress (Chen, 2001; Baumann, Boons; Bragd, 2002; Berchicci and Bodewes, 2005; Dangelico and Pontrandolfo, 2010) and creating authorities to monitor the progress. As the governing authorities are keen to monitor the law and order, health and safety, and similar aspects of governess, it is the hour to set the standards for sustainability as well. Many of the present sustainability claims are merely marketing ploys that do not benefit society in any way. (Ahern, L., Bortree; Smith, 2013; Baum 2012; Carlson, Grove; Kangun, 1993; O'Connell, 2010; Parguel, Benoit-Moreau; Russell, 2015; Saha & Darnton, 2005; Segran, 2019; Sicotte, 2009). An example can be taken from the textile industry, where a garment with as little as 5% recycle or organic fibre can be labelled as 'sustainable' (www.close-the-loop.be). When it comes to recycling claims, it can sometimes cost more in terms of chemicals and resources to generate a subpar product than new production (Sandin and Peters, 2018). Such assertions are anticipated to have a free run without a rational standard, which might be regarded as defrauding society.

As a result, the question becomes: Who sets the boundaries?

Relying upon one of the initial reports on sustainable development, The Brundtland report (1987) recommends that the responsibility for sustainable development lies with national decision-makers and with the international community. They also suggest the role of industry in the sustainable movement. The industry is on the leading edge of the interface between people and the environment. Both industry and governments stand to benefit from working together to secure a healthy environment (The Brundtland Report, 1987). In the current

social situation, any meaningful change in society can be imparted by combined efforts from international bodies, governments and industries. Past experiences have shown that the public is prone to manipulation and does not seem to have a big say, and the best example is 'consumerism' itself.

In general, a top-down strategy is critical so that businesses can implement policies uniformly. In the absence of regulatory policy, businesses will always be at risk of losing business to competitors who do not follow the same concerns.

Consumer research shows that the majority of people are willing to accept sustainable products if they are accessible (Chase and Smith 1992; White, Habib and Hardisty, 2019). One of the most significant barriers to consumers choosing a sustainable product is the lack of information on the product's sustainability (Delmas and Burbano, 2011). An average person cannot check all the details behind the market's sustainability claims for products. Governing authorities are supposed to deliver that information to customers under this proposed paradigm. Thus, customers will not have to choose between dramatically different research findings that are applied to diversified goods.

2.4. What is the Sustainable-Consumerism Concept?

In today's world, demand growth is the most important component in determining economic growth, regardless of whether the economy is capitalist, socialist, or mixed. Any ideology that stands in the way of demand growth will be neglected by industry and governments. The proposed method aims to establish sustainability without challenging the current system but by altering only one component, namely the product, and rearranging the other factors around it. This proposed model is not attempting to hinder demand growth; instead, it attempts to achieve sustainability by delivering where it matters. All other elements expect to remain unchanged or alter minimally.

The 'Sustainable-Consumerism' concept can be further explained with a metaphor from the fast-food industry that stands for easily and quickly available food at affordable prices. Constant advertising motivates consumers to buy it but, largely unhealthy food choices are provided. This proposed model will retain the principal character of fast food, but instead of unhealthy choices, it will provide healthy alternatives to the consumers. In other words, all other aspects of the business will remain usual; the consumer will be receiving advertisements as earlier, availability and affordability will be taken care of, and at the same time, a healthy alternative will be offered. If a policy change of this proposed model is applied, it will be less harmful to the industry, government and public at large on economic terms as it will have a positive effect on public health and expenditure on healthcare. Under 'Sustainable-consumerism', a similar shift is recommended for most of our consumer goods.

From an end-user point of view, the paradigm of sustainable consumerism described here is based on converting standard items to sustainable ones in terms of durability, repairability, recyclability, and decomposition-ability while keeping the rest as is. In this approach, policymakers are expected to pass legislation to make products more sustainable in terms of the raw materials utilised and fair procurement. Anything which is not a basic need and not sustainable is taxed heavily. Handmade products and the use of craftsmanship should be promoted irrespective of geographical origin. Tax revenue should use to fund the repair business, reducing the need for early disposal. Plastic and petroleum by-products should use in moderation, which means that low-cost plastic products should be replaced with alternatives like metals, rubber, paper, wood etc. This change will make recycling more meaningful and valuable.

Low-cost, low-quality goods should be wipe-out from the shop shelves. Because these standards are intended to apply to the entire industry over a fixed time frame, a competitor selling a similar product at a lower price which results in a loss of sales could be prevented. When natural resources are employed to manufacture most products, the cost of natural resources rises, resulting in increased returns for farmers, regardless of their geographic location. In addition, the disposal of repairable, long-lasting products will generate a secondary market. The cooperation of government-supported community service organisations and other groups committed to a sustainable future can help to encourage repair and reuse even more.

2.5. How does it work in the real term?

To Conclude, the current economic development system is established on low-cost, high-quantity products, which should replace with more expensive, long-lasting (quality-based) items. For example, if a person wants to buy one pen from a supermarket, he can get a cheap pen for 0.20 cents per unit, with a minimum purchase unit of ten units. (Basically, this is how consumerism occurs; a requirement for one pen will lead to the purchase of ten of them since they are inexpensive!) This must be legally substituted with \$2 per unit in the proposed model, and the client has the option to buy a refill at a lower price. The industry should keep the profit margin the same as or even higher than selling ten pens; accordingly, governments will receive the same or higher taxes. Consumers will have to pay more, but they will receive a superior product in a quantity that is adequate for them. In this proposed model, when their needs were one pen and were stimulated to purchase ten of those, the necessity to store the remaining nine pens will be eliminated. Customers' income is expected to rise because of being a part of this supply chain.

This model is suggested to be implemented in a top-down manner, implying that international groups and governments will be required to enact necessary regulations to make products more sustainable products that are used and thrown away should be outlawed or substantially taxed so that their use is not cost-effective for buyers. In this regard, there would be no threat from competitors in the industry because the laws impact the entire business community equally. The cost of trash management will be lowered for governments. For the customer, as they will have a quality product at a competitive value, that can be used for a longer time and can be repaired, which is a win-win situation. Small-scale industries and craftsmanship will be in demand again in the industrial sector, which could aid social prosperity. Farmers and landowners will benefit from this shift to a renewable resource since their products will be in demand. Hopefully, the planet will be able to survive for a long time.

The proposed model of Sustainable consumerism is much different from the current usage of this term, which is used as an alternative for sustainable consumption. Table 2 explains this in brief.

Table 2. The difference between 'Sustainable consumerism' and 'Sustainable Consumption'.

Serial no.	Proposed sustainable consumerism	Current sustainable consumption / Green consumerism
1	It is a passive action for customers	It is an active action for customers
2	Not a fully conscious decision by customers	Fully conscious decisions by customers

3	Can retain the joy of "consumerism"	May feel guilty about Consumption
4	Influenced by "general perception"	Influenced by sustainability activism
5	No need for vast formal knowledge for decision making	Need a vast formal knowledge for decision making
6	Inspired by external factors like advertisements, social influence etc	Inspired by self-awareness / mindful consumption
7	Vast majority of the population can be brought in	Only a handful of educated people can follow it
8	Top-down approach	Bottom-up approach
9	Mindfulness by the means of advertisement, social influence and legality	Mindfulness by own decisions
10	Broader scope	Limited scope
11	Less perfect solution for the environment	Perfect solution for the environment
12	Economy will be less affected	If becomes a mass movement, economy may be severely affected
13	Joint efforts by industry, Government and consumers needed	Efforts by sustainability enthusiasts and consumers sought
14	More practical approach	Less practical approach for daily life
15	Can apply to a wide range of fields	Practically applicable only to the field in which the customer is aware

3. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER THOUGHTS

One of the immediate threats could be the overexploitation of natural resources due to higher demands for the same. As a result, laws must ensure that renewable natural resources such as Rubberwood, Bamboo, Palm leaves, Betel nut palm leaves, banana plant parts, hay from rice, wheat, or other food crops, and so on should promote. A plethora of alternatives can be found in traditional items used by various cultures. The simplest approach to achieving a sustainable lifestyle is to go back in time and combine it with technological progress. Unlike plastic, these compounds will aid in the creation of rural incomes through collection and production, particularly in developing nations.

'Sustainable-consumerism' is a macroeconomic concept that deals with government and industry policy changes. As a result, finding empirical evidence will be difficult until some country adopts it, even though empirical proofs can be found for sustainable products, secondary markets, government-supported recycling, and other few aspects of the concept, but not for the entire concept.

More studies are required to explore the economic impact of this concept, which is significant for deciding the boundaries for long-term and short-term goals.

To attain sustainability, organizational and management theorists must work outside of the present structure (Shrivastava, 1995). Sustainable consumerism, based on the concept of a product is a solution within our current economic system. It is the moment to think of a structure beyond capitalism or socialism; it is the juncture to think of 'Sustainablism'. The term 'Sustainablism' refers to an economic structure in which the environment takes precedence over profit in conjunction with socialism that transcends national boundaries.

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